

Roadmap for Implementing the Open Science Development Strategy

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This roadmap serves as a comprehensive plan for the phased implementation, monitoring, and continuous improvement of open science initiatives at Berdyansk State Pedagogical University, ensuring alignment with global standards and fostering a culture of transparency, accessibility, and collaboration in scientific activities.

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Objectives of the Roadmap

- Ensure the continued development of existing open science initiatives and the implementation of new objectives.
- Identify responsible structural units and executors.
- Plan resources for supporting and expanding open science infrastructure.

- 1 **Updated Regulatory Documents:** Alignment of university policies and regulations with **Open Science** principles.
- 2 **Adopted Policies:** Implementation of agreements and guidelines, including the **Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment, DORA**, the **European Charter for Researchers**, and the **Code of Conduct for the Employment of Researchers**.
- 3 **Number of Training Seminars Conducted:** Count of workshops and training sessions related to open science principles and tools.
- 4 **ORCID Adoption Rate:** Percentage of faculty members with **registered and fully completed ORCID** profiles.
- 5 **Repository Integration:** Integration of the **institutional repository** with **international platforms** such as **OpenAIRE** and **EOSC**.

- 6 **Open Access Projects:** Number of scientific projects supporting **open-access principles**.
- 7 **Data Management Plan (DMP) Usage:** Availability and adoption of **DMP templates** for university researchers.
- 8 **DOAJ-Indexed Journals:** Number of university journals compliant with **DOAJ standards** and indexed in **DOAJ**.
- 9 **Open Research Datasets:** Number of open research datasets deposited in **thematic repositories** (e.g., **Zenodo**).
- 10 **FAIR and CARE Compliance:** Percentage of research datasets aligned with **FAIR** and **CARE principles** (at least one dataset per scientific project).
- 11 **FAIR and CARE Training Events:** Number of training activities conducted on adherence to **FAIR and CARE principles**.
- 12 **Annual Open Science Reports:** Regular publication of **annual reports** on open science implementation progress.
- 13 **Open Citations Integration:** Integrating university publication metadata into **open citation platforms** (*Initiative for Open Citations, I4OC*).
- 14 **Grant Applications and Projects:** Number of submitted and successfully implemented **open science grant projects**.
- 15 **Citizen Science Projects:** Number of implemented **citizen science projects** (at least one pilot project).
- 16 **Library Consultations:** Number of consultations the library provides on **data management** and **open-access journal selection**.
- 17 **Involvement in the Ukrainian Reproducibility Network:** Active participation in **national initiatives on reproducibility**.
- 18 **National Seminar on Research Reproducibility:** Organization of a **national seminar on reproducibility**.
- 19 **Guidelines on Predatory Journals:** Development and dissemination of **instructions to avoid publishing in predatory journals**.
- 20 **Use of Open-Source Software:** Increased adoption of **open-source software for data analysis** across research projects.

Responsible Parties for Implementing the Open Science Development Concept

- Vice-Rector for Research
- Research Department
- Head of Postgraduate Studies
- Committee on Research Ethics
- Technology Transfer, Innovation, and Intellectual Property Unit
- Open Science Implementation Working Group
- Research Institute for Educational Leadership
- Information and Computing Center
- University Library
- Deputy Deans for Research

- Heads of Departments
- Leaders of Research Projects and Departmental Research Topics
- International Relations Department
- ArsDocendi Teaching Excellence Center

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Monitoring and Reporting Mechanisms

- **Annual Reports:** Regular annual reports on **open science implementation progress** published on the **university's official website**.
- **FAIR and CARE Compliance Audits:** Periodic **independent audits** to assess adherence to the **FAIR and CARE principles**.
- **Integration into Annual Research Reports:** Inclusion of **open science indicators** in the university's annual scientific activity reports.
- **Researcher Participation Monitoring:** Regular tracking of researcher engagement in **open science practices**, including the use of **preprints, repositories, and open-access journals**.
- **Feedback Surveys:** Regular **surveys of researchers and faculty** to evaluate the effectiveness of training programs and institutional support for open science.
- **Open Science Metrics in Ranking Systems:** Enhancement of the **university's ranking system** to include **open science metrics**, such as **open data** and **open peer reviews**.
- **Grant Project Tracking:** Monitoring the **number of submitted and successfully implemented grant projects** aligned with open science principles.
- **Citizen Science Participation Analysis:** Evaluation of **citizen science project activity**, including the number of **participants** and **pilot initiatives implemented**.
- **Journal Indexing Audits:** Assessment of **university journals' accessibility and indexing**, including compliance with **DOAJ requirements** and audits of journal websites.
- **Publishing Policy Compliance:** Regular review of the **university's publishing policies** and updates to **author guidelines**.
- **Digital Tool Effectiveness:** Monitoring the **efficiency of digital tools** for managing data, preprints, and research results.
- **Internal and External Audits:** Conducting **internal and external audits** to evaluate the **quality and transparency** of open science implementation processes.
- **Promotion of Results:** Disseminating **achievements through participation in scientific forums, conferences, and seminars**.
- **Working Group Coordination:** The **Open Science Implementation Working Group** will coordinate monitoring processes and prepare **analytical reports**.

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Resources for Implementing the Open Science Development Concept

Human Resources:

- Specialists in Information Technology (IT specialists).
- Research Data Management Specialists (Data Stewards).

- Experts in Open Science and Digital Tools.
- Editors of Scientific Journals.
- International Activities Coordinator.
- Data Management and Open Access Journal Selection Consultants.
- Faculty and researchers involved in implementing open science policies.
- Administrative staff to support organizational processes.

Financial Resources:

- Securing grant funding for open science projects.
- Obtaining funding through research contracts.
- Flexible incentive system for active participation in open science implementation.
- Investments in digital infrastructure to support open data and publications.

Technical Resources:

- Expanding the functionality of institutional repositories.
- Integration of repositories with international platforms (OpenAIRE, EOSC).
- Digital tools for research data management (e.g., Data Management Plan).
- Platforms for data processing and analysis (e.g., R, Python).
- Systems for supporting open citations (Initiative for Open Citations, I4OC).
- Technical solutions ensuring compliance with FAIR and CARE principles.
- Updated university journal websites with user-friendly functionality.
- Monitoring and analytics systems for evaluating open science implementation.

Organizational Resources:

- Open Science Implementation Working Group.
- ArsDocendi Teaching Excellence Center.
- Library as a center for open science support.
- International Relations Department for coordinating global partnerships.
- Committee on Research Ethics.
- Technology Transfer, Innovation, and Intellectual Property Unit.
- Research Department (NDC).

Risks and Mitigation Strategies

- **Insufficient Awareness Among Researchers About Open Science Principles**
Mitigation Strategy: Conduct regular **training seminars, webinars, and consultations** to enhance researchers' awareness and skills.
- **Resistance to Change and Low Motivation for Implementing Open Science Practices**
Mitigation Strategy: Introduce a **flexible incentive and recognition system** for achievements in open science and actively communicate the benefits of adopting open practices.

- **Limited Technical Capabilities and Outdated Infrastructure**
Mitigation Strategy: Invest in developing digital infrastructure, modernizing repositories, and implementing new **technical solutions** to support open data.
- **Lack of Coordination Between University Departments**
Mitigation Strategy: Establish and activate the **Open Science Implementation Working Group** and ensure **clear communication channels** between departments.
- **Lack of Sustainable Funding for Open Science Projects**
Mitigation Strategy: Attract **grant funding**, establish **research contracts**, and **build partnerships** with international organizations.
- **Absence of Unified Standards for Research Data Management**
Mitigation Strategy: Develop and implement **Data Management Plan (DMP) templates** and adapt the **FAIR and CARE principles** into the university's internal policies.
- **Risk of Publishing in Predatory Journals**
Mitigation Strategy: Develop **guidelines for faculty and researchers** on avoiding publications in **predatory journals** and conducting **training events**.
- **Low Integration of University Resources into International Platforms**
Mitigation Strategy: Integrate **university repositories with OpenAIRE and EOSC**, and actively participate in **international initiatives** such as **I4OC**.
- **Challenges in Long-Term Support for Institutional Repositories**
Mitigation Strategy: Regularly monitor **repository performance** and involve **technical experts** to ensure the stable operation of systems.
- **Low Public Engagement in Scientific Projects**
Mitigation Strategy: Organize **pilot citizen science projects** and conduct **educational campaigns** to promote public involvement in science.